

A Comparative Study of the Resilience in Patients with Schizophrenia and Bipolar Affective Disorder

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Abstract:

Background: Resilience is the capacity to bounce back from adversity. Severe mental illnesses are associated with poor and heterogeneous functional outcomes.

Objective: To compare the resilience between patients diagnosed with schizophrenia and bipolar affective disorder.

Materials and Methods: The present study was conducted in a tertiary mental care hospital. It is a hospital based cross sectional comparative study done in patients diagnosed with schizophrenia and bipolar affective disorder with the help of Resilience scale and qualitative interpretation of resilience scale. Statistical analysis was done by using IBM Statistical package for the social science version 26

Results: In this study resilience scores in schizophrenia were lower than in bipolar patients and there was significant difference in resilience scoring between the two groups.

Conclusion: The resilience of an individual is an important factor to assess the patient's wellbeing. The aim of the treatment plan should include developing resilience in a patient and the need to plan for additional health care support during crisis periods when resilience is low.

Keywords: Resilience, Schizophrenia, Bipolar affective disorder, better outcome.

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Introduction

Resilience is the ability to adapt effectively and quickly to stressful or traumatic events, without regressing to one's initial state. It's a dynamic process shaped by biological, social, and environmental influences and is fundamental for growth of positive psychology which deals with satisfaction, adaptability, contentment, and optimism in people's life [1]. Human beings have the capacity to protect themselves and deal with the adverse events or stimulus, which can challenge their psychobiological homeostasis. And It is in this respect that resilience emerges as a crucial defense mechanism and protective factor when humans face challenging situations or stimuli that disrupt their psychobiological balance, allowing them to safeguard themselves and adapt effectively [1].

Resilience is a successful adaptation despite adversity and this personality trait has the potential to add new knowledge about how to achieve a successful outcome but has been understudied in

schizophrenia [2]. Resilience is positive growth or adaptation that mediates rates of recovery following periods of homeostatic disruption [3]. The concept describes a dynamic process of a person's coping capacity related to risk factors. Risk factors are stressful life events e.g., health problems, financial hardship, or problems at work or with family relationships and an increased possibility of a person to develop a mental health condition e.g., inherited vulnerability from a parent [4].

It has increasingly been recognized that poor adaptation to social context and more specifically deficient resilience in the face of adversity, is impaired in patients with both schizophrenia and bipolar disorder [5]. It is often conceptualized as existing along a continuum of vulnerability. Individuals with low vulnerability have a high resistance to psychopathology, although they are not entirely invulnerable to the development of a psychiatric disorder, such resistant individuals

often referred to as being resilient [3]. High level of resilience works a protective factor and lower level of resilience increases vulnerability for developing pathological consequences of adverse environmental events [1].

Aim:

To compare the resilience in patients diagnosed with Schizophrenia and Bipolar Affective Disorder visiting psychiatry OPD in a tertiary care center, Visakhapatnam.

Objectives:

- To assess the resilience of patients diagnosed with schizophrenia visiting Government Hospital for Mental Care, Visakhapatnam.
- To assess the resilience of patients diagnosed with bipolar affective disorder visiting Government Hospital for Mental Care, Visakhapatnam.
- To compare the resilience between patients diagnosed with schizophrenia and bipolar affective disorder.

Materials and Methods:

Study Design: A hospital based cross-sectional comparative study.

Study Setting: Government Hospital for Mental Care, Visakhapatnam.

Study Population: In-patients and out-patients diagnosed with Bipolar affective disorder and Schizophrenia as per International Classification of Diseases -10th Edition.

Sampling Method: Non-probability convenient sampling

Sample Size: 60 subjects were recruited by convenient sampling method (30 patients diagnosed with schizophrenia and 30 patients with bipolar affective disorder).

Inclusion Criteria:

- Age group: from 18 to 60 years.
- Patients diagnosed with Bipolar affective disorder and schizophrenia according to ICD 10 diagnostic criteria.
- Patients who have given valid written informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with epilepsy, intellectual disability, developmental disorders.
- Patients with substance dependence disorders (except nicotine).
- Patients with other severe medical illness.
- Patients not willing to give informed written consent for the study.

Methodology: The current study is a cross sectional study done in patients of Schizophrenia and Bipolar affective disorder attending the Out-patient and the In-patient wards of Government Hospital for Mental Care, Visakhapatnam.

The study was conducted after obtaining proper permission from the college authority and after obtaining clearance from the Institutional ethics committee of Andhra Medical College. Patients who fulfilled the criteria for bipolar affective disorder and schizophrenia according to icd-10 were approached for the study. Nature of the study was explained, and Informed written consent was taken from all the study participants who were willing to participate in the study. For those who were illiterate, the consent was read out and explained to them and consent was obtained by taking their thumb impression. Confidentiality of the study subjects was maintained.

Demographic variables were collected using a proforma which is used in the hospital, which includes: Age, sex, marital status, education, employment status, family pattern, and address of residence and a semi-structured interview schedule being used at hospital was used to aid for the psychiatric history taking.

Resilience scale was applied to both the patient groups, scores were collected, and data was analyzed with appropriate statistical tests.

Study Tools:

1. Consent form.
2. Semi-structured questionnaire for socio-demographic data.
3. Resilience scale by Dr. Vijaya Lakshmi & Dr. Shruthi Narain.

Consent Form: A self-designed informed consent form, which explained the nature of the study, was prepared. The contents of the consent form were explained in the vernacular language and were read out to the subjects. The signatures or left thumbprints (in case of illiterates) of the subjects consenting to the study were taken.

General Information Sheet: A self-designed form was used to collect the personal and socio-demographic details of the subjects. The form contained questions concerning the data for identification like name, age, gender, marital status, educational status, occupational status, socioeconomic status, and place of residence.

Resilience Scale by Dr. Vijaya Lakshmi & Dr. Shruthi Narain: Four dimensions in scale are perseverance, composure, self-reliance and faith.

Perseverance: It means persistence in doing something despite difficulty or delay in achieving success.

Composure: It refers to the state of being calm and in control of one self.

Self-reliance: An individual’s reliance on one’s own powers and resources rather than others.

Faith: It denotes complete trust or confidence in someone or something.

Total items in the scale are 30, of which 26 are positive and 4 are negative items. The scoring of positive items of Resilience scale was done by giving a score of: 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 for ‘Strongly Agree’ ‘Agree’ ‘Neutral’ ‘Disagree’ and ‘Strongly Disagree’ and negative items were scored as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 respectively. a total score of 150.

Table 1:

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Positive	5	4	3	2	1
Negative	1	2	3	4	5

Table 2: Qualitative interpretation of Resilience scale scoring:

Scores	Interpretation
122 and above	High resilience
84 to 122	Average resilience
Below 84	Low resilience

Statistical Analysis:

Statistical analyses were conducted using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences Ver16. Continuous variables were expressed as mean and standard deviations.

Categorical variables expressed as proportions.

Appropriate statistical tests were used to compare the resilience between the two groups.

Results:

Gender: Out of 60 patients; Males - 73.3% (n=46) and Females - 26.7% (n=14) with mean age of 32.63 and a standard deviation of 8.413.

Figure 1: Gender

Education: From the total sample illiterates were 15% (n=9), primary education 25% (n=15) and secondary education 43.3% (n=26) intermediate 5% (n=3) and graduates being 11.7% (n=7).

Figure 2: Education

Employment Status: From the total sample employed consisted of 36.7% (n=22) and unemployed 63.3% (n=38) respectively.

Figure 3: Employment Status

Resilience scores of 98.60 ± 6.821 in bipolar disorder and 75.13 ± 7.925 in schizophrenia patients respectively.

Table 3:

BPAD	N	Valid	30
		missing	0
		Mean	98.60
		Median	98.00
		Std. Deviation	6.821
		Range	27
		Minimum	83
		Maximum	110

Table 4:

BPAD	N	Valid	30
		missing	0
		Mean	75.13
		Median	75.00
		Std. Deviation	7.925
		Range	34
		Minimum	61
		Maximum	95

There is significant difference between resilience scores in bipolar patients and schizophrenia. P value is 0.000001 i.e. <0.05 so p value is significant.

Discussion

The capacity to which resilience is able to act as a preventative measure seems to have a strong correlation to ingrained psychosocial factors. The factors that act to maintain and uphold resilience are active coping, cognitive flexibility, and social support.

In this study we aimed to find out the resilience scores in patients of Schizophrenia and bipolar affective disorder and if there were any difference in resilience between these two patient groups. In this study lower resilience scores were seen in patients of schizophrenia which were similar to a previous study by Deng M et al. that showed lower resilience scores both in patients recently diagnosed as well as in chronic schizophrenic spectrum disorders when compared with healthy controls.

In this study resilience scores in bipolar affective disorder patients were comparatively higher than in schizophrenic patients which were similar to a previous study by Datta A et al. In this study resilience scores in schizophrenia were lower than in bipolar patients and there was significant difference in resilience scoring between the two groups. However, in a previous study by Mizuno et al., results showed total resilience scores significantly lower in patients with schizophrenia and bipolar disorder patients than in healthy controls, although the difference between the patient groups was not significant. Altogether, both schizophrenia and bipolar disorder patients show deficits in resilience, especially patients who recently received a diagnosis of schizophrenia

spectrum disorder. Even in the patients with remitted state of bipolar disorder, resilience level was significantly lower than healthy individuals.

Conclusion

The resilience of an individual is an important factor to assess the patient's well-being. The aim of the treatment plan should include developing resilience in a patient and the need to plan for additional health care support during crisis periods when resilience is low. The more we learn about resilience, the more potential there is for integrating salient concepts of resilience which may be crucial in the field of preventive psychiatry.

Limitations: This study did not assess resilience levels with severity of positive symptoms and general psychopathological symptoms which could have been more interesting. Major limitation is this study being cross-sectional, conducted in a single Centre with less sample size and hence the results cannot be generalized.

Future Recommendations: Need for more longitudinal follow up studies by using more strict methodology in a larger representative sample.

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